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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Micro-Electronics Radiation response variability for COTS devices Used in harsh Radiation environments</i>
Project TA identifier	TA09-281
General application	<i>Space, high-energy accelerators, COTS</i>
Type of test	SEE
Group leader, Institute	<i>Ivan Slipukhin, CERN</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	<i>Daniel Söderström, Mario Sacristán Barbero, and Rubén García Alía, CERN</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>2024-04-25 and 2025-01-14</i>
Facility	RADEF
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	20

Objectives of the experiments

Lack of traceability and radiation effect response variability are huge issues to overcome for the reliable utilization of COTS electronic devices in the space environment. In 2023 CERN has started a project co-financed by ESA to explore potential methodologies to be applied to solve this issue. They are meant at taking advantage of the large procurements that CERN typically does with respect to the smaller ones used in the space field. It will also study the possibility of using alternative testing techniques (e.g., laser) to assess the response of device to ion stimuli and bound intra-lot and inter-lot variabilities. In the context of this experiment, a set of devices was tested with heavy ions to collect information on SEE cross sections, and to study the variability of cross sections between DUTs.

Thanks to the data collected within this proposal it is possible to explore heavy ion SEE variability response in a wide variety of devices. This might shed more light on how to bound potential part-to-part variability when far less devices are tested because of smaller lot procurements and tested sample sizes. Cross section curves as a function of LET, and visualized data on the differences between the number of collected SELs per DUT are presented in this report.

The data shown here were presented at the NSREC REDW in 2025 [1], together with data from other test campaigns performed within the same project.

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Experiment test report

Tested devices and setup

Single-event latch-up (SEL) was the main type of effect studied in the tested devices. The tested device references are listed in *Table 1* Table 1, together with the function the device has, such as low-dropout (LDO) regulator, analogue to digital converter (ADC), digital to analogue converter (DAC), or operational amplifier (Op-Amp). The studied effects in the devices are also listed, and apart from SEL, single-event upsets (SEU) and single-event functional interrupts (SEFI) were also investigated in the tested FLASH memory device.

Table 1: Device references tested at RADEF in the experiment

Reference	Function	Effects studied
LT3083EQ#PBF	Low Drop-Out (LDO) regulator	SEL
AD7291BCPZ	Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC)	SEL
ADS8320	Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC)	SEL
AD7801BRUZ	Digital-to-Analog Converter (DAC)	SEL
OPA2192	Operational amplifier	SEL
IS25LP128-JBLE	128 Mbit FLASH memory	SEL, SEU, SEFI

The DUTs were mounted on dedicated daughter boards, connected through ribbon cables to SEE Tester boards [2], which in turn were connected to a PC used to interface with the SEE Tester and control the test procedures. Daughter boards mounted in the RADEF vacuum chamber are shown in Figure 1, where the larger green boards on the top rows contain devices from Table 1: boards with 9 DUTs of the same reference in a grid pattern in the left figure, and 8 DUTs of the same reference in a circular pattern in the right figure. All 8 or 9 DUTs of the same type (on one daughter board) were irradiated simultaneously in the same beam window.

Figure 1: DUT boards mounted in the RADEF vacuum chamber.

The 10 and 16.3 MeV/n [cocktails available at RADEF](#) were utilized during the test, containing ions with surface LET values between 1.52 and 85.6 MeV/(mg/cm²). All tests were performed in vacuum, without specific temperature control or monitoring.

Results

Measured SEE cross-section results and information of the observed part-to-part variability under irradiation are presented for each of the tested components in the following sections.

LT3083EQ, LDO

The SEL cross section data for the LDO linear regulator are shown in Figure 2, together with fitted Weibull function parameters. The data at the LET value of 9 MeV/(mg/cm²) was obtained while having 150 μm of Kapton in front of the DUTs while using the 16.3 MeV/n Ar-beam. The error bars represent 95 % confidence limits based on Poisson statistics of the SEL count, together with a 10 % estimated fluence uncertainty.

Figure 2: The SEL cross section results per device for the linear regulator LT3083EQ#PBF

The variability in the number of SEL counts per DUT at each run is shown in Figure 3, where the average and standard deviation of the number of SELs per DUT is shown graphically. This information is shown in table form as well in Table 2.

Figure 3: Variations in the number of SELs observed in the various DUTs tested in parallel of the LT3083EQ#PBF

Table 2: Number of SELs per device in the LT3083EQ#PBF

LET (MeV/(mg/cm ²))	Total SEL sum	Average SELs per DUT	SELs standard deviation
1.52	364	45.50	9.82
2.3	332	41.50	6.80
7.2	407	50.88	11.66
9	360	45.00	6.48
13.3	504	63.00	10.14
24.5	458	57.25	5.04
38.8	341	42.63	10.55
48.5	535	66.88	15.38

AD7291BCPZ, ADC

The SEL cross section data for the ADC AD7291BCPZ are shown in Figure 4, together with fitted Weibull function parameters. The data at the LET values of 16 and 18.5 MeV/(mg/cm²) was obtained while having 100 and 150 μm of Kapton in front of the DUTs respectively, while using the 16.3 MeV/n Fe-beam. The error bars represent 95 % confidence limits based on Poisson statistics of the SEL count, together with a 10 % estimated fluence uncertainty.

Figure 4: SEL cross section results per device for the ADC AD7291BCPZ

Figure 5: Variations in the number of SELs observed in the various DUTs of the ADC AD7291BCPZ

Table 3: Total, average, and standard deviation of the SELs per DUT of AD7291BCPZ

LET (MeV/(mg/cm ²))	Total SEL sum	Average SELs per DUT	SELs standard deviation
13.3	3	0.38	1.06
16	6	0.75	1.39
18.1	6	0.75	0.89
18.5	16	2.00	2.39
24.5	58	7.25	4.20
31.3	128	16.00	9.23
38.8	254	31.75	14.45
47.5	462	57.75	24.02
58.5	401	50.13	19.18
85.6	504	63.00	23.85

The variability in the number of SEL counts per DUT at each run is shown in Figure 5 and in Table 3. This DUT had the largest fluctuations in the observed SEL counts, due to one DUT (DUT6) showing a lower cross section response than the others. DUT5 on the other hand, was behaving in line with the other DUTs for some runs, e.g. the 1100-MeV Ag run using the 10 MeV/n cocktail, but after some time and a few runs the DUT started to have considerably more SELs than the others. The DUT5 is then suspected to have had some malfunction during the test, and it has been excluded from the average cross section curve in Figure 5, as well as from the results shown in Table 3.

ADS8320, ADC

The SEL cross section data for the ADC ADS8320 are shown in Figure 6, together with fitted Weibull function parameters. LET values below 20 MeV/(mg/cm²) did not result in any SELs, and only the upper cross section limits are shown in the figure for these data points.

Figure 6: Device SEL cross section results for the ADC ADS8320

The variability in the number of SEL counts per DUT at each run is shown in Figure 7 and Table 4.

Figure 7: Variations in the number of SELs observed in the various DUTs of the ADC ADS8320

Table 4: Total, average, and standard deviation of the SELs per DUT of ADS8320

LET (MeV/(mg/cm ²))	Total SEL sum	Average SELs per DUT	SELs standard deviation
13.3	0	0.00	0.00
16	0	0.00	0.00
18.5	0	0.00	0.00
24.5	128	14.22	3.82
31.3	678	75.33	12.99
38.8	540	60.00	7.41
47.5	629	69.89	7.82
58.5	533	59.22	6.49
85.6	494	54.89	4.28

OPA2192, Op-Amp

The SEL cross section data for the Op-Amp OPA2192 are shown in Figure 8 *Figure 2*, together with fitted Weibull function parameters. The variability of the number of SEL counts per DUT at each run is shown in Figure 9 and Table 5.

Figure 8: Device SEL cross section results for Op-Amp OPA2192

Figure 9: Variations in the number of SELs in the Op-Amp OPA2192 DUTs

Table 5: Total, average, and standard deviation of the SELs per DUT of the OPA2192

LET (MeV/(mg/cm²))	Total SEL sum	Average SELs per DUT	SELs standard deviation
7.2	5	0.63	0.70
9	37	4.63	2.18
13.3	278	34.75	6.10
24.5	539	67.38	9.64
38.8	544	68.00	6.54
48.5	513	64.13	4.68

AD7801BRUZ, DAC

The SEL cross section data for the DAC AD7801BRUZ are shown in Figure 10, together with fitted Weibull function parameters. The variability of the number of SEL counts per DUT at each run is shown in Table 6 and Figure 11.

Figure 10: Device SEL cross section results for DAC AD7801BRUZ

Table 6: Total, average, and standard deviation of the SELs per DUT of the DAC AD7801BRUZ

LET (MeV/(mg/cm ²))	Total SEL sum	Average SELs per DUT	SELs standard deviation
9.7	486	60.75	14.42
13.3	471	58.88	11.13
24.5	484	60.50	9.64
38.8	579	72.38	4.21
48.5	456	57.00	8.53
85.6	410	51.25	7.43

Figure 11: Variations in the number of SELs in the AD7801BRUZ DUTs

IS25LP128-JBLE, FLASH memory

The FLASH memory IS25LP128-JBLE was also irradiated during the test, with 6 operational DUTs tested in parallel. They were irradiated in active and passive mode. In active mode the memory arrays of the DUTs were sequentially read and checked for SEUs and re-written during the irradiation, and in passive mode the memory arrays were written with a known pattern before irradiation, and then checked for upsets after irradiation. In all tests, the pattern “AA_{hex}” was utilized for writing to the memory array. The analysis for the active mode tests is not shown here in this report, but the observed average SEU cross sections of the bits in the memory arrays during passive mode irradiation as a function of LET are shown in Figure 12. The data are based on the average SEU statistics of the irradiated 128 Mbit FLASH memories.

Figure 12: Device SEU cross section for the FLASH memory

The observed cross sections separated per DUT are shown in Table 7 for each tested LET value, and the variability plots are displayed in Figure 13. The cross sections observed at high LET values are similar among the DUTs, while there are considerably more variations observed at low LETs.

Table 7: Device SEU cross section (cm²/bit) for each FLASH DUT tested in parallel

LET (MeV/(mg/cm²))	9.7	13.3	24.5	38.8	48.5
DUT1	$5.40 \cdot 10^{-15}$	$1.33 \cdot 10^{-15}$	$2.57 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$1.37 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$6.15 \cdot 10^{-12}$
DUT2	$1.42 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$1.33 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$4.22 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$2.09 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$4.85 \cdot 10^{-12}$
DUT3	$1.47 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$9.27 \cdot 10^{-15}$	$2.84 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$2.99 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$4.22 \cdot 10^{-12}$
DUT4	$1.37 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$3.05 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$4.59 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$4.38 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$5.37 \cdot 10^{-12}$
DUT5	$2.85 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$3.71 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$7.06 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$6.44 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$5.87 \cdot 10^{-12}$
DUT6	$7.22 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$2.38 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$4.40 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$3.60 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$5.27 \cdot 10^{-12}$

Figure 13: Variations in the number of SEUs in the IS25LP128-JBLE DUTs

Conclusions

Part-to-part variability was investigated mainly based on the analysis of the SEL cross-sections of the studied devices. IS25LP128-JBLE Flash memories did not experience any SELs, however, their variability analysis was performed with the collected SEU statistics.

The differences between event cross-section estimates can originate from multiple sources, and, apart from part-to-part variability, can be influenced by the beam flux uncertainty, test board misalignment, and low event statistics. Hence, a definite conclusion about the influence of part-to-part variability is not possible in most of the studied devices (especially in the cases of overlapping cross-section error margins), although a certain divergence of the mean cross-section values is always present. Based on the analysis of this parameter, it can be concluded that in the verified range of LETs, the cross-section discrepancies of the tested part references remained within a factor of two. The most pronounced evidence of part-to-part variability was found in the AD7291 (ADC) irradiation results. In particular, the DUT5 is characterized but up to 5 times higher than average SEL cross-section at LETs below 24.5 MeV/(mg/cm²). As the increased SEL sensitivity of DUT5 appeared at a later stage of the test campaign, it cannot be excluded that at certain point this DUT suffered from a permanent radiation-induced failure, causing the observed cross-section enhancement. On the other hand, DUT6 was characterized by significantly lower than average SEL statistics, in which SEL counts were close or equal to 0 at all tested LETs. Here, a possibility of the DUT damage before the irradiation (e.g. in the delidding or soldering processes) cannot be excluded. In all other tested devices, as well as for other AD7219 DUTs, the SEL cross-sections typically remained within the error bars of all the components irradiated simultaneously.

The variability of SEU cross-section of the Flash memory device demonstrated a significant increase up to a factor of 28 at lower LET values. The cross-section estimates tend to converge towards higher LETs, and are the smallest at 48.5 MeV/(mg/cm²). It should be noted, that the uncertainty of low-LET cross-section calculation has been significantly impacted by low SEU statistics, which were often less than 50 per DUT during irradiations at particular LETs.

References

- [1] D. Söderström, I. Slipukhin, M. Sacristán Barbero, M. Poizat, T. Borel, H. Kettunen *et al.*, "Single-Event Latch-up Data from Heavy-Ion Irradiation of COTS Components with Inter-Lot Variability Study", presented at the NSREC REDW 2025, July 14-18, 2025, Nashville, TN, USA.
- [2] I. Slipukhin, A. Coronetti, R. García Alía, F. Saigné, J. Boch, L. Dilillo *et al.*, "Enhancement of system observability during system-level radiation testing through total current consumption monitoring", IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci., vol. 71, no. 8, pp. 1948–1955, 2024, doi: 10.1109/TNS.2024.3424201.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	X

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

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